

D3.2

Co-created UI/UX design

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
UI	User interface
UX	User experience
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
TMS	Transport Management System
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
ITU	Intermodal Transport Unit
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TOS	Terminal Operating System
CMR	Convention des Marchandises par Route (Convention on the International Carriage of Goods by Road)
e-CMR	Electronic CMR (Convention des Marchandises par Route)
API	Application Programming Interface

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1. Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to present the results of T3.2, “Co-created UI/UX design” which is part of WP3, “Toward Plug & Play Implementation”. WP3, which started on M13 and will end in M25, aims to design and develop a functional web app interface and backend for supporting the demonstration scenarios (WP4). According to the architecture designed for a secured and accessible application (T3.1) and to the technologies embedded for ensuring that relevant stakeholders are transversally protected against various criticalities related to different cyber risk degrees (T3.3), the web app user interface is designed (T3.2) and here described. Afterwards, the web app itself will be developed (T3.4).

This document describes the methodology adopted to co-create the UI/UX design. In particular, the four main steps of the methodology will be described.

1. Analysis and assessment, see Sect. 3.
2. User experience, see Sect. 4.
3. User interface, see Sect. 5.
4. Test and handoff, see Sect. 6.

The final remarks and the conclusion of the deliverable are given in Sect. 7.

Further to this document, the final output of T3.2 is provided with the design file (.fig) that has been created by using Figma¹, a collaborative web application for interface design. This file will support the development of the KEYSTONE web app (T3.4) and has been deposited under open access on the Zenodo platform² (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083516>)

In conclusion, this report and the design file are expected to support:

- T3.3 (WP3) at ensuring that key cyber security controls are embedded in the KEYSTONE web app;
- T3.4 (WP3) at developing the web app;
- T4.2 (WP4) at formalizing and describing the demonstration scenarios;
- T5.1 (WP5) at providing ad-hoc KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) regarding the usability and the accessibility of the web app;
- T6.2 (WP6) at providing concrete outputs to share with stakeholders keeping them engaged.

¹ <https://www.figma.com/>

² <https://zenodo.org/>

2. UI/UX design: a co-creation approach

This document aims to describe the design of the KEYSTONE web app user interface (T3.2). By ensuring that key cyber security controls are embedded in the KEYSTONE solution (T3.3), finally, the web app itself will be developed (T3.4) and will support the piloting activities (WP4).

To design the UI/UX of the KEYSTONE web app, a “co-creation” methodology has been adopted and here described. This methodology is a collaborative approach that places users and stakeholders at the centre of the design process to ensure the creation of web applications that are intuitive, functional, and aligned with business goals. It involves iterative phases of analysis, ideation, and prototyping, combining user insights, design thinking, and market research to address pain points, define user flows, and optimize information architecture. The methodology emphasizes stakeholder engagement, usability, accessibility, and continuous refinement to deliver web applications that enhance user satisfaction and meet organizational objectives.

The co-creation approach is composed of 4 main steps.

1. Analysis and assessment, see Sect. 3. This phase is a foundational step in the co-created UI/UX design methodology, aimed at mapping features and content of current and similar products while identifying customer pain points and potential opportunities for improvement. This phase involves a detailed evaluation of user needs and business objectives through various activities. Key actions include identifying pain points and friction areas from demonstration scenarios, mapping opportunities that deliver business value, and uncovering unmet customer and business needs through design thinking workshops with stakeholders. Additionally, customer behaviours, market dynamics, and emerging trends are analysed to provide a holistic understanding of customer interactions and capture unmet needs. The outcomes of this phase include clearly defined task objectives, a detailed profile of target users with their needs and requirements, and a preliminary set of product features, setting the stage for the subsequent design and development processes.
2. User Experience (UX), see Sect. 4. This phase focuses on shaping the new user experience by optimizing the information architecture and refining the layout to ensure usability and accessibility. This phase begins by envisioning and mapping user flows for core users, aligning them with user requirements to define and prioritize features that deliver value. The information architecture is meticulously structured to create a smooth and intuitive experience, guiding the design of portal pages and content blocks. Efforts are directed towards enhancing customer satisfaction by refining information architecture, content strategy, and interactions, emphasizing functionality over aesthetics. The process involves mapping new user flows, content hierarchy, and product structure, resulting in a cohesive layout that supports both usability and accessibility goals. The outcomes of this phase include detailed user flows, a robust information architecture, and wireframes that serve as proofs of concept (PoC) for the envisioned experience.
3. User interface (UI), see Sect. 5. This phase focuses on translating the defined user experience into a visually compelling and pixel-perfect design. This stage establishes the new look & feel of the web application, ensuring consistency with brand guidelines while enhancing aesthetics and usability. The process begins with creating the visual design for key pages based on previously developed wireframes, aligning naming conventions and definitions with the new information architecture. A cohesive mood board and style guide are developed to reinforce brand recognition and convey the product’s value. The UI design follows atomic design principles, starting from fundamental elements to build components and templates, ensuring scalability and consistency. Additionally, assets and UI components are prepared for seamless developer handoff. An interactive mockup (without coding) is also created to validate the overall product design and user interactions before implementation. The key outcomes of this phase are a fully designed user interface with all necessary assets and components, as well as an interactive mockup that provides a tangible preview of the final product.

4. Test and hand off, see Sect. 6. This phase ensures that the designed user experience is validated with end users and refined based on real-world feedback before moving into development. This phase involves user testing sessions, where participants interact with the prototype while their behaviours are observed and documented using the think-aloud approach. Additionally, usability, usefulness, and acceptance are measured through surveys based on the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), providing quantitative insights into user satisfaction. Feedback is collected, analysed, and shared with stakeholders to validate necessary improvements or change requests. Before finalizing the design, internal and external user testing is conducted to ensure approval and alignment with expectations. Once validated, design assets and specifications (such as Figma files) are meticulously prepared and handed off to developers (T3.4), ensuring a seamless transition into implementation.

3. Analysis and assessment

This is the first step of the co-created UI/UX design methodology. The main activities are given by:

- analysing the tools that are currently used by stakeholders, see Sect. 3.1;
- identifying pain/friction points and needs from demonstration scenarios (T4.2), see Sect. 3.2;
- collecting customer and business unmet needs by design thinking workshops, see Sect. 3.2.

3.1 Analysis of existing tools/web app

The goal of this task is to map features and content in current products and other similar products identifying customer pain and product opportunities. A preliminary analysis comes from the output of D1.3 (KEYSTONE, 2024) which describes the main tools used by all the actors in the transport and logistics sector. Freight terminals, public enforcement, and logistic operators have their platforms. These platforms are different, and the managed data varies according to the specific platform type, see Figure 1.

The main European platforms used by enforcement authorities are:

- ERRU: a specialized platform designed to enable the exchange of information between national registers concerning the validity of community licences and the infringements committed by transport companies in foreign territories;
- RESPER: an interconnected database of European driving licence archives;
- IMI: a system used by European national authorities to communicate data, including companies posting workers, between each other;
- TACHOnet: a telematic network to facilitate communications about tachograph cards;
- Movehub: a pivotal platform facilitating interconnection among various authorities, enabling the sharing of information sourced from the registers of new member states;
- Euris: a platform that provides information on transport operations in inland navigation;
- eFTI: a regulation whose aim is to make faster road transport through digitalization;
- EUCARIS: an application that facilitates the exchange of mobility-related information among Member States using a peer-to-peer exchange model.

Other public platforms explored are:

- Port community system (PCS): a tool used by port authorities to expedite port operations through the digitization of administrative and control processes;
- Drive Belt: Italian governance support tool aimed at collecting, homogenizing, and valorising Italian logistics and transport data coming from public administration systems and the actors of the digital logistics chain.

Regarding private platforms, instruments used by freight terminal operators are:

- Terminal operating system (TOS): a digital system used to manage and optimize the operations of a terminal.

Regarding private platforms, tools used by transport operators are:

- Transport Management System (TMS): an end-to-end software used by transport companies to manage logistics and streamline shipments;
- Moova EasyRailFreight: a platform accessible to logistic operators that provides various services related to the offer of transports on the market and tracking of goods.

Figure 1. Main tools used by all the actors in the transport and logistics sector - source D1.3 (KEYSTONE, 2024).

According to the analysis of the stakeholders' needs of D1.1 (KEYSTONE, 2024) and of the data exchange platforms of D1.3 (KEYSTONE, 2024), several gaps emerge in examining the current data exchange scenarios in freight transport and the stakeholders' needs. These gaps affect the realization of a fully digitalized data exchange ecosystem in the transportation sector. In particular, it is evident that:

- a lack of robust safety and security measures discourages stakeholders from using single platforms for data exchange;

- interoperability issues hinder the integration of diverse systems used by logistic operators and freight terminals, particularly in international contexts, together with the absence of technological standards;
- the absence of a real-time single interface for mandatory data exchange complicates processes, fostering inefficiencies and increasing operational costs.

To achieve a digital logistic ecosystem is crucial to focus on interoperability, standardization, regulatory harmonization, and stakeholder collaboration.

3.2 Internal assessment for eliciting requirements

The goal of this activity is to collect customer and business unmet needs. To elicit the requirements of the KEYSTONE web app, a co-design workshop has been organized with the KEYSTONE partners and stakeholders. A fundamental input for supporting the co-design workshop is given by T4.2 which has defined and described the demonstration scenarios in terms of pain points and needs.

The workshop's goals, setup, activities, and outcomes are described in the following sections.

3.2.1 Co-design workshop's goals

The workshop goal was to discover and verify user needs and requirements, and to gather the necessary inputs for shaping the KEYSTONE web app experience, including its key features, datasets, APIs, and any other essential elements. The KEYSTONE web app aims to facilitate seamless data exchange during inspections and it is targeted to the enforcement authorities (e.g. road police enforcer, port authority) and the transport operators (e.g. truck drivers).

The output of T4.2 was used as a starting point for the workshop activities since it provides a clear overview of the challenges the KEYSTONE web app should try to address and enhance. T4.2 made a comprehensive analysis of the KEYSTONE scenarios with a focus on the pain points and opportunities in each step of the itinerary. The two scenarios are the following.

1. *Road transport digital ecosystem*: this scenario focuses on a road transportation of a container from northern Italy to the Port of La Spezia, where the container is loaded on a ship with a destination in a country outside the EU. The enforcement authority involved is the port authority and the pilot aims to establish a data exchange with the port authority. This pilot will be implemented in T4.3.
2. *Intermodal transport digital ecosystem*: this scenario involves goods departing from the Rotterdam intermodal hub, traveling by train to CIM Novara, and then being loaded onto a truck for their final destination. During the road journey, the road police enforcer stops it to ensure compliance with regulations and the safety of the transport. This pilot will be implemented in T4.4.

3.2.2 Co-design workshop set up

An online 6-hour workshop was held on 29th October, using the Miro³ software as a collaborative tool. The workshop was organized as a co-creation session where all the stakeholders were invited to produce outcomes that would be of value to them and, in turn, to the business.

The stakeholders invited are the WP3 and WP4 partners (Cefriel, CIM, Gruber Logistics, Aethon, ICOOR, Coventry, Etelätär, T Bridge, STA, RINA) and the Port of La Spezia representatives.

Before the workshop, a general architecture of the web app was presented to the participants, see Figure 2. According to the output of T4.2, the target users of the web app were defined as:

³ <https://miro.com/it/>

- the port authority operator;
- the truck driver;
- the road police enforcer.

For simplicity, these users will be the main actors in the piloting activities (T4.2, T4.3, T4.4). In particular, the port authority operator and the truck driver will be demonstrated in the “road” scenario, while the road police enforcer will be demonstrated in the “intermodal” scenario.

Figure 2. The general architecture of the KEYSTONE web app.

For each target user a “persona” was defined to help the workshop participants empathize with the target users, understand their needs and pain points, and design products or services that meet their expectations and goals. Personas are fictional characters that are created based on research to represent the different user types that might use the app. In the following tables, the three created personas are described in terms of profiling characteristics (role, experience, location, age), job activities to perform, pain points, and opportunities (identified in T4.2).

Persona 1 – Road scenario: Port authority officer

MARCO ROSSI

Experience: 10 years in port operations
 Role: Port authority officer
 Location: Port of La Spezia
 Age: 40

Doing

- Verify the identity and authorization of drivers and vehicles entering the port.
- Maintain a secure environment by thoroughly checking all incoming and outgoing goods with vehicles.
- Ensure all operations comply with local, national, and international regulations.
- Management of traffic conditions at the port entrance.
- Update the terminal system with entry data for tracking and management.

Pain Points

- Port does not have drivers' information in advance.
- Driver might be stopped at the Port gate because he/she does not have permission to get in.
- The high volume of traffic leads to congestion and increased waiting times.
- Communication gaps with logistics companies cause inefficiencies.

Opportunities

- Availability of container and driver's data to Port in advance.
- Utilizing real-time data analytics for better traffic management.
- Collaborating with stakeholders to streamline entry processes.
- Digitizing the CMR document (Convention des Marchandises par Route) for simplifying administrative management.

Persona 2 – Road scenario: truck driver

MATTEO CARLINO

Experience: 10 years in long-haul trucking
 Role: Truck driver
 Location: Based in Rotterdam, frequently travels across Europe
 Age: 35

Doing

- Transport containers from the customer to the Port of La Spezia.
- Ensure timely and safe delivery of goods.
- Maintain compliance with road safety and transportation regulations.
- Update logistics offices about loading status and departure times.
- Handle and verify necessary documents such as CMR, licences, truck registration, and goods documentation.
- Handle paper CMR documents (Convention des Marchandises par Route) and ensure they are signed at the Terminal.

Pain Points

- Time-consuming paper-based documentation and verification.
- Reliance on calls can result in delayed updates and miscommunication.
- Handling physical CMR documents is cumbersome and prone to errors.
- Expired documentation (badge) leads to potential delays for being stopped at Port gates due to lack of pre-authorization.

Table 1. Long waiting time at port gate.

Opportunities

- Develop a centralized platform for seamless communication and data sharing.
- Implementing automated notifications for check-in and unloading status can streamline processes.
- Digitizing CMR documents would simplify administrative tasks and reduce errors.

- Enhance the flow of information between terminals, logistics offices, and drivers.
- Establishing a system for pre-authorizing drivers can prevent delays at Port entry.

Persona 3 – Intermodal scenario: road police enforcer

ALEX MARTINEZ

Experience: 15 years in law enforcement

Role: Road police enforcer

Location: North Italy

Age: 40

Doing

- Identify and stop trucks that may need checks based on compliance data.
- Conduct truck inspection.
- Check driver's, vehicle's, and goods' documentation.

Pain Points

Table 2. Doesn't know when the truck leaves the freight terminal.

- Paper documents consume a lot of time for the check.
- Needs to connect a lot of different systems to check all the information.
- No possibility of checking trucks without stopping them.
- No data is available about the flow of trucks on the road to set up the checkpoints.

Opportunities

- Automate the process of capturing information/data about the truck and goods.
- Possibility to track the real-time location of trucks.
- A solution that allows remote control of trucks.
- Unique entry point to connect to different systems.
- Digital Repository of all required paper documents available in a unique system.

3.2.3 Co-design workshop's activities

The workshop was organized as follows.

- **Introduction.** An explanation to all participants about the context of the two use cases, a summary of the pain points and opportunities (T4.2), and an overview of the workshop activities.
- **Group activities.** Participants are divided into 2 groups: the first group focuses on the intermodal scenario, while the second group focuses on the road transport scenario. The first group is asked to think of themselves as the "road police enforcer" persona. The second group is asked to think of themselves as the "port authority operator" and the "truck driver" personas. Each group is asked to perform the following activities:
 - **Activity 1 - Collection of user needs and requirements:** identifying which are the core needs of their persona and highlighting actions and data required for achieving core needs;
 - **Activity 2 - Turn the needs into ideas:** designing the features of a new web app that could support the needs identified in Activity 1 and, optionally, trying to sketch the most voted functionalities.
- **Final sharing session:** each group presents the outcomes and ideas of the group, followed by an open discussion between participants.

Both activities were performed on the Miro tool by using ad hoc boards and templates to simplify the collaboration among participants. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show respectively the boards used for Activity 1 and Activity 2.

Activity 1 starts with the discussion and agreement of all participants on the user goal since it is the focal point for all the subsequent tasks. Then participants are asked to write down all the needs of the personas in the specific use case. After a brief discussion, the most important needs are selected and copied on the third board where they are further analyzed in terms of the actions the personas have to do to reach the expected outcome and the kind of information required.

Figure 3 Co-design workshop - Activity 1 boards.

Activity 2 starts from the output of Activity 1 and aims to turn the needs into ideas, by thinking of a web app that could help the personas in their activities. Participants are asked to ideate the features and functionalities of the KEYSTONE Web App necessary to support the selected personas’ needs. Participants are also asked to try to imagine the flow of the KEYSTONE web app and to sketch the features on a mobile phone/tablet interface.

Figure 4 Co-design workshop - Activity 2 boards.

3.2.4 Co-design workshop’s outcomes

The following paragraphs describe the outcomes of the port authority, truck driver, and road police groups.

3.2.4.1 Port authority outcomes

The group activities started with the discussion and agreement of all participants on the port authority goal in the road transport scenario. They agreed on the following: *“Improved efficiency at port entry points, achieved through streamlined processes, and enhanced security will be ensured with automated systems, better coordination and management for traffic management and signification reduction in waiting time”*.

Bearing this in mind, the activities continued with the definition of the core needs of the port authority personas and of the main web app functionalities. The Miro board resulting from these activities is displayed in Figure 5.

Figure 5 Co-design workshop - Outcomes of Port Authority

After the workshop, the collected needs were processed and clustered according to their high-level needs. Table 1 displays the full list of identified needs and Table 2 cross-references each suggested web app feature with the corresponding needs.

Table 1 Port Authority needs.

Need-id	Needs	High-level needs
PA-N1	The port authority would like to receive alerts for any delays or changes in trucks ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival)	Real-Time Information and Alerts
PA-N2	The port authority would like to access real-time updates on truck positions and routes.	
PA-N3	The port authority would like to receive updated information on traffic conditions.	
PA-N4	The port authority would like to display all the upcoming trucks with updated ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) information	Efficient Traffic Management at the Port Gate
PA-N5	The port authority would like to plan and schedule truck arrivals to minimize waiting times at the port gate.	
PA-N6	The port authority would like to inform trucks arriving at the port in case of congestion at the port gate.	
PA-N7	The port authority would like to use automated systems to improve the efficiency at entry points.	

PA-N8	The port authority would like to coordinate with terminal needs for loading and unloading.	Efficient Port Management
PA-N9	The port authority would like an application integrated with the Port Community Systems for seamless operations.	
PA-N10	The port authority would like to collect and store driver and truck company information.	Driver and Vehicle Data Management
PA-N11	The port authority would like to match driver and container data efficiently.	

Table 2 Port Authority proposed features.

Need-id	Proposed web app features
PA-N1, PA-N2, PA-N3, PA-N4, PA-N5	A centralized platform for real-time data visualization and alerts.
PA-N1, PA-N2	Display of real-time trucks ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) or trucks position.
PA-N1, PA-N2	A search bar where the port authority can put licence plates and get information about ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival).
PA-N1, PA-N6, PA-N7	Alerts notification (if any delay).
PA-N5, PA-N6, PA-N7	Notification to the driver to stop the truck or to continue to the gate in case of delay.
PA-N10, PA-N11	Uploading and storing driver's documents.
PA-N10, PA-N11	Scan the licence plate for checking.
PA-N10, PA-N11	Scan a QR code that allows access to a variety of data (truck, company, goods, shipment).
PA-N10, PA-N11	Sections for personal data, vehicle data, company data, cargo data, and shipment data.

To clearly define the objective and scope of the port authority web app, needs were prioritized and only the most relevant ones were considered in the subsequent phases of the web app design process.

The main goal of the port authority web app will be to support the port authority officer in the management and optimization of the traffic flow at the port gate, through a system of alerts and real-time information sharing between the port and the logistic operators. Therefore the web app will focus on the high-level needs of “Real-Time Information and Alert” (PA-N1 and PA-N3) and “Efficient Traffic Management at the Port Gate” (from PA-N4 to PA-N7).

3.2.4.2 Truck driver outcomes

The workshop activities started with the discussion and agreement of all participants on the truck driver goal in the road transport scenario. They agreed on the following: *“Efficient operations through real-time data sharing and digital documentation. Key processes include pre-arrival coordination, arrival check-ins, container handling, and compliance with e-CMR documentation (Electronic CMR). These measures ensure timely delivery and enhanced coordination between ports and logistics providers”.*

Bearing this in mind, the activities continued with the definition of the core needs of the truck driver personas and of the main web app functionalities. The Miro board resulting from these activities is displayed in Figure 6.

Figure 6 Co-design workshop - Outcomes of truck driver

After the workshop, the collected needs were processed and clustered according to their high-level needs. Table 3 displays the full list of identified needs and Table 4 cross-references each suggested web app feature with the corresponding needs.

Table 3 Truck driver needs.

Need-id	Needs	High-level needs
TD-N1	The truck driver would like to know what time to arrive at the port gate.	Real-Time Information and Alerts
TD-N2	The truck driver would like to receive alert notifications in case of queue or disruption at the port gate.	
TD-N3	The truck driver would like to be informed about any queues or delays at the port gate.	
TD-N4	The truck would like more information about the destination gate (e.g. gate number).	
TD-N5	The truck driver would like to have driver and truck documents in digital format.	Document digitalization
TD-N6	The truck driver would like a digital process for the verification of his/her driving licence and truck documents to streamline the compliance checks.	

Table 4 Truck driver proposed features.

Need-id	Proposed web app features
TD-N1, TD-N2, TD-N3	Real-time updates and alert notifications.
TD-N1, TD-N2, TD-N3, TD-N4	Have a sort of "traffic light" that indicates if it is possible to reach the port gate or not, and which gate.
TD-N5	A section about vehicles, cargo, driver, and shipment data.
TD-N4	Map of the port with information to find easily the gate.
TD-N1, TD-N2, TD-N4	Section with information about the destination port.

To clearly define the objective and scope of the truck driver web app, needs were prioritized and only the most relevant ones were considered in the subsequent phases of the web app design process. The main goal of the truck driver web app will be to support the driver in sharing ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) updates in case of disruption during the journey and in receiving updates from the port gate about the best time to reach the port gate. Therefore the app design will be focused on the high-level needs “Real-Time Information and Alert” and, in particular, on the needs TD-N1, TD-N2, and TD-N3.

3.2.4.3 Road police outcomes

The workshop activities started with the discussion and agreement of all participants on the road police enforcer goal in the intermodal scenario. They agreed on the following: *“Efficient monitoring of truck flow with minimal disruption, a comprehensive inspection process that ensures compliance and enhances road safety, with all findings digitally recorded for accountability”*.

Bearing this in mind, the activities continued with the definition of the core needs of the road police personas and the main web app functionalities. The Miro board resulting from these activities is displayed in Figure 7.

Web APP Features /Functionalities

30 min

Turn the needs into ideas, Think of a web App that supports selected outcomes, that can help Alex Road police

Figure 7 Co-design workshop - Outcomes of road police.

After the workshop, the collected needs were processed and clustered according to their high-level needs. Table 5 displays the full list of identified needs and Table 6 cross-references each suggested web app feature with the corresponding needs.

Table 5 Road police enforcer needs.

Need-id	Needs	High-level needs
RP-N1	The road police would like to check trucks remotely.	Remote Checks
RP-N2	The road police would like to know which trucks need to be stopped for physical control.	
RP-N3	The road police would like to access real-time valid information about departure and route to set up only targeted on-site checks.	Targeted On-Site Checks
RP-N4	The road police would like to plan the checkpoints of the day ahead.	
RP-N5	The road police would like to monitor trucks coming in/out from the CIM terminal.	Monitoring
RP-N6	The road police would access truck ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) information to know the upcoming trucks in a given area.	
RP-N7	The road police would like to monitor the forecast traffic conditions and special truck movements.	
RP-N8	The road police would like to be able to retrieve and check the driver data, goods, and truck given the licence plate of the truck.	Inspection and Verification
RP-N9	The road police would like a checklist of important data to be checked and their status (valid, not valid).	
RP-N10	The road police would like to access the history of the checks (number of checks, date...).	
RP-N11	The road police would like to submit completed checks and update the system.	
RP-N12	The web application must allow access to information with a few clicks.	Functional
RP-N13	The web application must be fast and user-friendly.	
RP-N14	The web application must be secure.	
RP-N15	The app should have access to the device location and camera.	

Table 6 Road police enforcer proposed features.

Need-id	Proposed web app features
RP-N14	Two-factor authentication (2FA) for secure access.
RP-N14	Role-based access control with different views (e.g., road police, admin).
RP-N14	Log-in credentials including name, password, and electronic identification (EID).

RP-N14	Device authentication.
RP-N9	Checklist of important data to be checked with red/amber/green indicators.
RP-N1, RP-N5, RP-N6	List of upcoming trucks in a given area with ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) information.
RP-N1, RP-N5, RP-N6	Live tracking of trucks on a map or list with filter options.
RP-N15	Push notification (with geo-fencing).
RP-N8, RP-N5, RP-N3	The source of information and date of last update are displayed.
RP-N11	Ability to manually mark trucks from red to green flag.
RP-N15	Evidence gathering with photo support.
RP-N13	Possibility to set up the default language.

To clearly define the objective and scope of the road police web app, needs were prioritized and only the most relevant ones were considered in the subsequent phases of the web app design process.

The main goal of the road police web app will be to support officers in remotely inspecting trucks, allowing them to stop only those with irregularities. It will also facilitate monitoring the flow of trucks expected to pass through a specific area and assist in the process of checking and verifying documents. Therefore the high-level needs selected are “Remote Checks” (RP-N1, RP-N2), “Targeted On-Site checks” (RP-N3), “Monitoring” (RP-N5, RP-N6), and “Inspection and Verification” (RP-N8, RP-N9, RP-N10, RP-N11). The functional requirements (from RP-N12 to RP-N15) will be taken into account throughout the entire design process.

4. User Experience (UX)

The User Experience (UX) phase is the second step of the co-created UI/UX design methodology. The main goal of this phase is to shape the web app user experience by optimizing the information architecture and refining the layout to ensure usability and accessibility. Starting from the prioritization and selection of needs described in Sect. 3.2.4, the main activities focused on the envisioning of the application flows and the creation of an intuitive and efficient journey for the users. The following paragraphs describe the user flow designed for the three views of the KEYSTONE web app. Finally, the description of the user flows has allowed us to identify the main features of the web app and, respectively, the data/information needed for implementing those features, see Annex 1. This activity has supported the technical partners (T2.2, T2.3, T3.1, T3.4 leaders) in cross-checking and validating the availability of all data necessary to implement the designed application flow.

4.1 Register/Log in flow

The user authentication and registration process is the same for the three views of the web app (road police, port authority, and truck driver). The user authentication must ensure the security and confidentiality of the data processed. The flow was designed starting from the requirements that emerged during the workshop about the necessity to have two-factor authentication (2FA) for secure access and role-based access control with different views (e.g., road police, admin). Figure 8 displays the registration and login flow. Users start by

either logging in or registering if they do not have an account. If logged in successfully, they proceed to security authentication and then access the home page. If not registered, users must enter personal details based on their profile type (road police, port authority, or driver). They provide information such as name, surname, and job role before submitting the registration. Once submitted, the system verifies the details through security authentication. Upon successful authentication, users gain access to the home page. This structured flow ensures a secure and role-based authentication process for different user categories.

Figure 8 Register/Log in flow.

4.2 Road police web app flow

The goal of the web app is to support road police enforcers in remotely inspecting trucks, allowing them to stop only those with irregularities, to facilitate the monitoring of the flow of trucks expected to pass through a specific area, and to assist in the process of checking and verifying documents.

To achieve these goals the user experience of the road police web app was designed as displayed in Figure 9. From the home page, officers can either view traffic updates or handle suspicion notifications for trucks. The "View Traffic Updates" section provides information on trucks approaching, entered, or exited from the CIM terminal, thus facilitating the monitoring of trucks' movements.

The "Suspecting notification for truck" section provides a list of the trucks with potential irregularities. For the trucks with issues, the list of driver, truck, and ITU (Intermodal Transport Unit) data is displayed on the app with a green/red flag according to the validity of the data. The officer can then assess the situation: if no issue is found, the check is conducted remotely, and data is saved. Otherwise, the truck undergoes physical inspection, and officers verify and confirm the problem (e.g. not valid document), flagging it accordingly or adding comments. The check details are then recorded and displayed on a dedicated section of the app, which can be consulted by the road police enforcer to get more information about the checks made in the past to a specific truck. If the issue is confirmed, an appropriate punishment is applied according to traditional regulations, outside the KEYSTONE web app.

Figure 9 Road police web app flow.

4.3 Port Authority web app flow

This web app aims to support the port authority in the management and optimization of the traffic flow at the port gate, through a system of alerts and real-time information sharing between the port and the logistic operators.

The designed user flow is displayed in Figure 10. The process begins in the “Manage Traffic Flow” section, where the system displays the number and the list of trucks that are about to arrive at the port gate, allowing for real-time monitoring of incoming traffic. The data about the truck's ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) are updated in real-time thanks to the sharing of information with the logistic operators.

If necessary, the port operator can manually send an alert to one or more trucks regarding possible congestion at the port gate. The alert is a text message that can be customized to provide additional details about the congestion.

Figure 10 Port Authority web app flow.

4.4 Truck Driver web app flow

The web app will support the driver in triggering the update of the Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA) in case of disruption during the journey (e.g., an accident occurring during the trip). Furthermore, the web app will allow the driver to receive updates from the port authority regarding the best time to reach the port gate. The designed user flow is displayed in Figure 11.

The process starts from the home page, where the driver can access two main functionalities. First, in the "Itinerary details and sending alert" section, the driver can view trip information, including origin, destination, and ETA. If a disruption occurs, the driver can send a notification to the Transport Management System

(TMS) for triggering/requesting an ETA recalculation. Additionally, in the second section “Notification about congestions”, the app displays notifications about congestions and delays sent by the port authority, informing the driver about the status of traffic at the port gate.

Figure 11 Truck driver web app flow.

5. User interface (UI)

The User Interface (UI) phase is the third step of the co-created UI/UX design methodology. The main goal of this phase is to create pixel perfect design for the main pages. The main activities are the visual design of the pages and the definition of the look and feel of the app aligned with the brand guidelines.

The outcomes are the design of the user interface (with all the assets, components and look and feel) and an interactive mockup to show the user flow through the different app pages. The interactive mockups were designed using the Figma⁴ software, namely a collaborative web app for user interface design. Along with the creation of the final mockups, the development of the app's wireframes has been undertaken. The work leading to the final mockups involved creating an initial version, which was validated during the mid-term review (see Section 6.1), followed by subsequent refinements based on the feedback received.

In this chapter, we describe only the final version of the mockups, along with a detailed explanation of the different views of the application.

⁴ <https://www.figma.com/>

5.1 Register/Log in mockups

To access all the KEYSTONE apps the user must be registered and logged in with the credential managed by the KEYSTONE application. Figure 12 displays how the login page will look like.

The mockup shows a login page with the following elements:

- Login** (Section Header)
- Please login to continue to your account. (Text)
- Username (Input field with a user icon)
- Password (Input field with a password icon)
- Log in (Button)

Figure 12 Login page mockup.

5.2 Road Police web app mockups

The Road Police App consists of 3 main pages: the “Home”, the “Inspection History” and the “Settings” page. This third page was not included in the scope of the mockup design, since it is not the core of the KEYSTONE web app.

At the top of the “Home” page, a personalized greeting message welcomes the user, who can select the preferred language for the app content.

The “Home” page consists of two main sections: the “Inspection Alerts” and the “Day Overview” sections, as displayed in Figure 13.

The “Day Overview” section aims to facilitate real-time truck monitoring by summarizing the truck movements involving the CIM Novara terminal. The number of trucks exiting, checked in, and scheduled to arrive at the CIM Novara terminal is displayed at the top of this section. Below, a detailed list of trucks is displayed, showing the licence plate, terminal, and truck status (“Checked in at *time*”, “Loading at *time*”, “Exiting at *time*”). A red flag indicates the trucks with issues that are also listed in the “Inspection Alerts” section.

The “Inspection Alerts” section highlights trucks with issues (such as trucks with invalid documents) providing key details like the truck's licence plate, logistics company, and the truck status. The road police can be guided by this list in the selection of the trucks to stop for the physical inspection. Once the truck is stopped, the road police can click on the button “Inspect” to initiate the inspection.

Figure 13 Road police mockup - Home page.

By clicking on this button, the road police can access the key information about the truck (licence plate number, route, logistics company, terminal, and the truck's loading status with the scheduled time), as displayed in Figure 14.

The popup displays also a "Document Checklist" section which allows the road police enforcers to review and validate essential documents. Each document is marked as either "Valid" or "Not Valid". In this example, the "Driving Licence" is flagged as invalid, due to the “Expiry Date” information, which is highlighted in red.

Road police enforcers can select invalid documents and either clear or confirm their status using the buttons at the bottom. This interface facilitates efficient and accurate document verification during roadside inspections.

Figure 14 Road police mockup - Truck details popup.

In case the road police enforcer wants to confirm the invalidity, the web app displays a new interface with the inspection log associated with a specific truck (identified by the licence plate number). The task is divided into two steps, "Invalidity confirmation" (see Figure 15) and "Inspection Details" (see Figure 16). In the "Invalidity confirmation" section, for each document, the officer can select a reason for invalidity from a dropdown menu, add relevant comments, and upload supporting evidence (such as images or documents). Then, to finalize the invalidity report, the officer must click on the "Confirm invalidity" button which leads to the "Inspection Details" phase where the officer adds the date, time, and location of the inspection to record it.

Figure 15 Road police mockup - Truck inspection popup (step 1).

Figure 16 Road police mockup - Truck inspection popup (step 2).

The second page of the web app is the “Inspection History” page, accessible by navigation icons at the bottom of the screen.

This page displays the list of all inspections done in the past, including the truck's licence plate number, company name, inspection date and time, location, and status (“valid” or “not valid”). The goal is to provide the officer with a tool for gathering further information about a given truck while he/she is conducting a roadside check.

The interface provides also a search bar that enables the user to input a truck's licence plate number to retrieve specific inspection details.

Figure 17 Road police mockup - Inspection history page.

5.3 Port Authority web app mockups

The Port Authority App consists of 3 main pages: the “Home” page, the “Alerts history” page, and the “Settings” page. This third page was not included in the scope of the mockup design, since it is not the core of the KEYSTONE web app.

The “Home” page consists of two main sections: the “Overview” and the “Traffic flow” sections, as displayed in Figure 18. The “Overview” section provides an overview of the status of trucks at the port gate, in particular, it includes the number of trucks that need to be alerted, those scheduled to arrive in the next two hours, trucks in a queue for checking, and trucks allowed to enter the port gate. The trucks to be alerted are automatically selected by the KEYSTONE application by taking as input the information about the trucks' ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) and the port gate congestion status. These key metrics aim to help port authorities efficiently manage the flow of trucks arriving at the port gate.

Figure 18 Port authority mockup - Home page.

Figure 19 Port authority mockup - Alert message popup.

The "Traffic Flow" section lists detailed information about each truck, such as licence plate numbers, company names, Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), and status. The ETA is continuously updated, according to the ETA changes shared by the logistic operators. The port authority officer can manually select the trucks to be alerted and proceed with the sending of an alert message. By clicking on the "Next" button, a pop-up will be opened, as displayed in Figure 19. Here the port authority officer can select one of the suggested messages and, if needed, customize the message with more details about the traffic congestion before sending it to the selected trucks. The alert message is sent to the TMS of logistic operators which is in charge of recomputing the ETA and sharing it with the truck driver.

Figure 20 Port authority mockup - Alert history page.

The second page of the web app is the "Alerts history" page, which lists all the sent alerts with the details of the licence plate numbers, the company names, and the time the alert message was sent.

5.4 Truck Driver web app mockups

The Truck Driver App consists of 3 main pages: the "Home" page, the "Messages" page, and the "Profile" page. This third page was not included in the scope of the mockup design, since it is not the core of the KEYSTONE web app.

The "Home" page, displayed in Figure 21, is designed to provide the truck driver with two main functionalities: receiving notification about possible delays in the destination place or viewing the journey status and sending messages to inform about changes in ETA (Estimated Time of Arrival) due to disruptions the driver encounter during the journey.

The "Incoming Messages" section displays unread notifications about alerts sent to the driver (e.g. queue alert from "Port of La Spezia" indicating long queues at the port gate and suggesting a break).

The "Trip Overview" section outlines the details of the current journey (shipment ID, departure time and location, pick-up time and location, and the final destination with estimated arrival times) and lets the driver call or message his/her company to inform about disruptions that occur. By clicking on the icons below the itinerary, the popup of Figure 22 will be displayed. It allows the driver to send an audio message to his/her assistant manager. This interaction mode was designed to ensure quicker and safer communication.

The second page "Messages", displayed in Figure 23, can be accessed by the navigation icons at the bottom of the screen. It contains the history of all the incoming (e.g. alerts messages from the port) and outgoing (e.g. messages about delays sent by the truck driver) messages.

Figure 21 Truck driver mockup - Home page.

Figure 22 Truck driver mockup - Send message popup.

Figure 23 Truck driver mockup - Messages page.

6. Test and hand off

The "test and handoff" phase is the last step of the co-created UI/UX design methodology. The main goal of this phase is to test and validate the app design with the end users, collect feedback for improvements, and hand off the final mockup version to the development team.

Two testing sessions were organized to test and validate the app at two different phases of the web app design: a mid-term review (see Sect.6.1) and a final user testing (see Sect. 6.2).

The first testing session was organized after the design of a preliminary version of the UX mockups with the KEYSTONE partners as testers to perform usability testing for improving the app user experience. The collected feedbacks were used as redesign recommendations and implemented in the final version of the mockups, described in Sect. 5. The second testing phase includes the testing of the final mockups with real end users (e.g. representatives of road police agents, port authority officers, and truck drivers). This test aims at measuring the “usability”, “usefulness”, and “acceptance” according to the main dimensions of the TAM (Technology Acceptance Model).

The process and tools used to hand off the final version of the mockups to T3.4 are described in Sect.6.3.

6.1 Mid-term review

A first usability test was performed in December 2024 for testing the first version of the mockups. Most of KEYSTONE’s partners (CIM, ICOOR, Etelatar, STA, UPM, CORTE, AETHON, AEC) were involved in the tests to collect feedback about the web app usability and to validate the web app user’s experience. The Cefriel team set up 10 testing sessions, organized as a one-to-one remote session of 30 minutes where each partner was asked to perform some tasks on an interactive prototype of the web app deployed with Figma. During the sessions, the moderator asked each partner to test the three views of the web app (road police enforcer, port authority, and truck driver app). Partners were asked to imagine being in three different scenarios and to perform some tasks on behalf of each KEYSTONE target user. While performing the tasks, the partners were asked to share their screens and to think aloud. The verbalization of their thoughts as they move through the app interface (e.g. what they are looking at, thinking, doing, and feeling) aims to help discover the misinterpreted design elements which then turn into actionable redesign recommendations.

At the end of the tasks the moderators collect feedback on the experience by asking a set of questions (listed in Table 7) about the ease of use and task completion, the clarity of information, and the visual design.

Table 7 List of questions for mid-term review.

Assessment dimension	Question
Ease of use and task completion	How easy was it for you to complete the task you were asked to do?
	Were there any obstacles or difficulties during the task?
	Were you able to complete tasks without confusion or frustration?
Clarity of Information	Were the instructions, labels, and notifications clear and easy to understand?
	Did you feel that the app provided enough information to help you make decisions?
Visual Design	Did the visual design (colours, fonts, buttons, etc.) make the app easy to use?
	Was the layout intuitive, and did it help you find what you needed quickly?

In the following paragraphs, we report the details of the test performed for each web app view and the main feedback collected.

6.1.1 The Road Police app

The scenario and task assigned to the users for the testing of the road police web app are the following.

- **Scenario:** imagine you are a road police agent at a roadside checkpoint. You are using the KEYSTONE web app to check the status of the trucks in the area to decide which trucks to stop at the checkpoint.
- **Task:** the app alerts you about some trucks with potential issues and you decide to inspect one of them, how would you do it?

The feedbacks collected during the sessions were then harmonized and summarized as shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24 Road police mockup - First version with feedback.

Overall, the road police web app received a positive assessment. As regards the “Ease of use and task completion” assessment, all the partners were able to complete the task without confusion. They appreciated the linear app flows and the simple and clear layout which allows them to access and find the information easily.

We collected some suggestions about the “Visual design” such as little changes in colours and icons to improve the user experience (e.g. change the base colour of the app and use red colour to indicate issues, highlights some information, etc.). Regarding the “Clarity of information”, some partners think that some information needs to be made more explicit and more detailed (e.g. reasons for “red flag”, details on the not valid data, etc.). They also suggest adding a page on the app to display all the past inspections to provide more information to the road police enforcer.

6.1.2 The Port Authority app

The scenario and task assigned to the users for the testing of the port authority web app are the following.

- **Scenario:** imagine you are the Port Authority officer of La Spezia port, and you are monitoring and managing the flow of trucks coming to the port. At the port gate, there are long queues of trucks waiting to be checked.
- **Task:** you want to inform the upcoming trucks about the queue. In particular, if you want to send an alert message to a Gruber Logistics truck expected at the port gate by 15:30, how would you do it?

The feedback collected during the sessions was then harmonized and summarized as shown in Figure 25.

Figure 25 Port authority mockup - First version with feedback.

Overall, the Port Authority web app was appreciated by the partners due to its simplicity and clarity of information. As regards the “Ease of use and task completion” assessment, all the partners were able to complete the task without confusion. As regards the “Visual Design” assessment, we collected some suggestions to make the interface more intuitive (e.g. better highlighting of trucks with alerts, titles in the overview blocks, etc.). We also collected a suggestion of a missing functionality that would be worth including (e.g. grouping functionality to send alerts to a set of trucks at once).

6.1.3 The Truck Driver app

The scenario and task assigned to the users for the testing of the truck driver web app are the following:

- **Scenario:** imagine you are the driver of a Gruber Logistics truck that is departing from the Novara CIM terminal and headed to the port of La Spezia terminal.
- **Task 1:** you receive a notification from the port of La Spezia about a delay at the port gate, how do you read it?
- **Task 2:** an hour later, unfortunately, you get stuck in the queue on the motorway. If you want to send a message to your company to inform them about the delay, how would you do it?

The feedback collected during the sessions was then harmonized and summarized as shown in Figure 26.

Figure 26 Truck driver mockup - First version with feedback.

Concerning the “Ease of use and task completion” assessment, the completion of the two tasks generates some confusion and frustration in the participants, due to a too complex screen flow.

As regards Task 1, partners suggest some “Visual Design” improvements to make the received notification more prominent on the home page. The small bell on the top right corner of the screen is hardly visible, especially for a person focused on driving.

As regards Task 2, too many clicks are required to reach the action button to send the alert message. Most partners agree that a quicker way to send a message directly from the home page is required to simplify the task for the driver who needs to complete the task with the least possible distraction. The possibility of sending the message as a vocal message was very appreciated.

6.2 Final user testing

A second test was performed in March 2025 to test the final version of the mockups with real users. The tests were performed with two groups of users: port authority officers, and truck drivers. The national highway patrol of Italy (“Polizia Stradale”) and the Financial Police (“Guardia di Finanza”), the Italian militarised law enforcement agency, have been officially informed about the KEYSTONE project. We've explored the opportunity of engaging them in the KEYSTONE activities, for example for testing the web app. Despite their active interest in following the progress of the project, an official commitment from the authorities is still pending. We'll keep on fostering their active engagement and we'll propose a test of the web app in the next weeks.

This testing phase aims to measure the “usability”, “usefulness”, and “acceptance” of the web app according to the main dimensions of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, 1989), a widely used approach for assessing digital product adoption.

The testing sessions were organized as one-to-one remote sessions, according to the following agenda.

1. **Introduction & Scope:** a brief explanation of the purpose of the app and its intended benefits.
2. **Walkthrough/Demo:** the key features and functionalities are presented to the user.
3. **User Interaction:** the user is asked to explore the app on his/her own. The interaction consists of imaging to be in the scenario described in Sections 6.1.2, and 6.1.3 and performing the assigned task.
4. **Brief questionnaire:** the user is asked to provide feedback by answering to few questions. The questionnaire was kept short and simple to minimize effort for users. The questions, displayed in Table 8, are based on the TAM model.

Table 8 List of questions for final user testing.

Question	Answer option
I find this app valuable.	Strongly Disagree → Strongly Agree (5 levels scale)
The interface is intuitive and easy to understand.	Strongly Disagree → Strongly Agree (5 levels scale)
I see myself using this app in the near future.	Strongly Disagree → Strongly Agree (5 levels scale)
How would you rate this app?	Not useful → Very useful (5 levels scale)

The answers given by the two groups of stakeholders are listed in Table 9.

Table 9 Answers from the 2 groups of stakeholders.

Question	Port Authority Answer	Truck Driver Answer
I find this app valuable.	5. Strongly Agree	5. Strongly Agree
The interface is intuitive and easy to understand.	5. Strongly Agree	4. Agree
I see myself using this app in the near future.	5. Strongly Agree	4. Agree
How would you rate this app?	5. Very useful	5. Very useful
Comments and suggestions.	<p>Display the name of the truck driver and check his/her badge validity to speed up the accessing process to the port.</p> <p>Opportunity to inform the truck driver about the ITU status (e.g., ready for pickup/loading).</p>	<p>Highlight the features of the app with different colors (notifications and sent messages) to differentiate them better.</p>

6.3 Hand off

The final mockup was handed off to T3.4 (“Development of a web app”) for the implementation of the KEYSTONE web app. The mockups were shared as a Figma file (.fig), ensuring a smooth transition between the design and development phases. The sharing of a Figma project helps deliver assets and components for development, speeding up the implementation of the application.

The file has been deposited under open access on the Zenodo platform (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15083516>).

7. Conclusions

This document represents the Deliverable “Co-created UI/UX design” (D3.2). It is the final part of T3.2 “Web app user interface” that is part of WP3, “Toward Plug & Play Implementation”. D3.2 describes the methodology adopted to co-create the UI/UX design. In particular, the four main steps of the methodology are here described: (i) analysis and assessment, (ii) user experience, (iii) user interface, and (iv) test and handoff. Further to this document, the final output of T3.2 is provided with the design file (.fig) that has been created by using Figma, a collaborative web application for interface design. This file will support the development of the KEYSTONE web app (T3.4) which has been deposited under open access on the Zenodo platform.

According to the definition of the demonstration scenarios (T4.2), the web app has been designed for three target users: (i) the port authority operator, (ii) the truck driver, and (iii) the road police enforcer. In particular, the web app has been designed to allow them the following tasks.

1. The port authority officer can manage the access of trucks heading to the port gate. By receiving the estimated time of arrival (ETA) of the trucks, the port can use the web app to alert the truck drivers about the status of traffic at the port gate.
2. The truck driver can optimize his trip operations. By using the web app, the driver can receive information about the status of traffic at the port gate and/or trigger the processing/updating of the ETA to be shared with the port authority.
3. The road police enforcer can optimize checks and inspections on trucks. By using the web app, the road police enforcer can be notified in advance (before stopping a vehicle) regarding those trucks and drivers that present irregularities, not valid documents (e.g., an expired driver's licence), etc.

Two testing sessions have been organized to test and validate the app. The first testing session was organized with the KEYSTONE partners as testers to perform usability testing for improving the app user experience. The collected feedback has allowed the redesign of the final version of the web app that has been tested by two groups of stakeholders: port authority officer and truck driver. The stakeholders have also shared a few suggestions and improvements.

Finally, the web app, fed with standard API (Application Programming Interface) (WP2), will allow to demonstrate the benefits of a digital ecosystem in two scenarios: the "road transport digital ecosystem" (T4.3) and the "Intermodal digital ecosystem" (T4.4).

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Annex 1

The annex displays the tables used as a collaborative tool to define the data required for implementing the KEYSTONE web app features. The web app features are mapped to the schema of the app flow displayed below the table.

Road Police web app

Branch name (fig. below)	ID	Web app feature	High-level information feeding the web app	API/Data provider	API/Data elaboration
View Traffic Updates	1	Display the total number of trucks that will enter to CIM terminal	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?), booking time (at CIM) planned to unload and load an ITU at CIM	GRUBER	1. sum of n. trucks ordered against booking time 2. visualization of a number (e.g., sum of trucks)
View Traffic Updates	1	Display the list of trucks that will enter to CIM terminal	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?), booking time (at CIM) planned to unload and load an ITU at CIM	GRUBER	visualization of a list of data
View Traffic Updates	2	Display the total number of trucks that entered to CIM terminal	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?), check-in time (at CIM) checked in at CIM	CIM	1. sum of n. trucks ordered against check-in time 2. visualization of a number (e.g., sum of trucks)
View Traffic Updates	2	Display the list of trucks entered into the CIM terminal	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?), check-in time (at CIM) checked in at CIM	CIM	visualization of a list of data
View Traffic Updates	3	Display the total number of trucks that exited from the CIM terminal	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?), check-out time (at CIM) exited from CIM	CIM	1. sum of n. trucks ordered against check-out time 2. visualization of a number (e.g., sum of trucks)
View Traffic Updates	3	Display the list of trucks that exited from the CIM terminal	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?), check-out time (at CIM) exited from CIM	CIM	visualization of a list of data
View Traffic Updates	4	Display the total number of trucks with issues	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?) planned to unload and load an ITU at CIM, checked in CIM and/or checked out from CIM + info to be checked by the road police officer (e.g., driver's licence, truck insurance, CMR, etc.)	GRUBER, CIM + European platforms (ERRU+T achronet, ...)	1. sum of n. trucks ordered against a temporal filter 2. visualization of a number (e.g., sum of trucks)
View Traffic Updates	4	Display the list of trucks with issues by a flag (e.g., "red" with issues)	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?) planned to unload and load an ITU at CIM, checked in CIM and/or checked out from CIM + info to be checked by the road police officer (e.g., driver's	GRUBER, CIM + European platforms (ERRU+T achronet, ...)	visualization of a list of data

			licence, truck insurance, CMR, etc.)		
View Traffic Updates	5	Display details of one truck (driver data, truck data, ITU data) with red/green flag for each info (elaboration by the app accessing data of European platforms)	Info about trucks, driver (& ITU?) planned to unload and load an ITU at CIM, checked in CIM and/or checked out from CIM + info to be checked by the road police officer (e.g., driver's licence, truck insurance, CMR, etc.)	GRUBER + CIM + European platforms (ERRU+T achonet, ...)	visualization of each single data, data comparison for identifying possible issues (e.g., expired dates of driver's licence)
Suspecting notification for truck	6	Display details of one truck (driver data, truck data, ITU data, status journey: arriving/entered/exited from CIM) with red/green flag for each info	Info about truck, driver (& ITU?) given a specific n. plate info to be checked by the road police officer (e.g., driver's licence, truck insurance, CMR, etc.)	GRUBER + CIM + European platforms (ERRU+T achonet, ...)	visualization of each single data, data comparison for identifying possible issues (e.g., expired dates of driver's licence)
Suspecting notification for truck	7	Save information about the checks (data verified, check status, date, country, police enforcer ID)	Info about truck, driver (& ITU?) given a specific n. plate + info to be checked by the road police officer (e.g., driver's licence, truck insurance, CMR, etc.) + id police enforcer (generated by web app)	GRUBER + CIM + European platforms (ERRU+T achonet, ...) + backend app data (id police agent)	save info about the check
Suspecting notification for truck	8	Verify and confirm issues (e.g. document not valid). Flag the right data issue and/or add text in a "comment" text area	Info about truck, driver (& ITU?) given a specific n. plate + info to be checked by the road police officer (e.g., driver's licence, truck insurance, CMR, etc.)	GRUBER + CIM + European platforms (ERRU+T achonet, ...)	visualization of each single data, data comparison (boolean?)
Suspecting notification for truck	9	Save information about the checks (data verified, check status, date/time, country, police enforcer id)	Info about truck, driver (& ITU?) given a specific n. plate + info to be checked by the road police officer (e.g., driver's licence, truck insurance, CMR, etc.)+ id police enforcer	GRUBER + CIM + European platforms (ERRU+T achonet, ...) + backend app data (id police agent)	save info about the inspection

Port Authority web app

Branch name (fig. below)	ID	Web app feature	High-level information feeding the web app	API/Data provider	API/Data elaboration
Manage traffic flow	1	Display the number of trucks that are about to come from Gruber	Info about trucks, driver, ITU planned to reach the port (all transportation managed by Gruber, both Gruber and other providers trucks) + updated ETA	GRUBER	1. sum of n. trucks ordered against updated ETA 2. visualization of a number (e.g., sum of trucks)
Manage traffic flow	1	Display the list of trucks that are about to come from Gruber	Info about trucks, driver, ITU planned to reach the port (all transportation managed by Gruber, both Gruber and other providers trucks) + updated ETA	GRUBER	visualization of a list of data
Manage traffic flow	2	Alert a specific driver about possible congestions at the port gate - the port manually triggers an alert for the driver (no portual data are needed) + the port operator can send a textual message elaborating the alert	Info about trucks, driver, ITU planned to reach the port (all transportation managed by Gruber, both Gruber and other providers trucks) + updated ETA	GRUBER	set the list of trucks/drivers to be notified by an alert (e.g., trucks arriving in a specific time slot)+ text box for allowing the port operator to write a message to the driver

Port Authority Web app

Truck driver web app

Branch name (fig. below)	ID	Web app feature	High-level information feeding the web app	API/Data provider	API/Data elaboration
itinerary details	1	Display itinerary details (origin, destination, ETA)	data about shipment: customer detail, port destination, updated ETA	GRUBER	visualization
itinerary details	2	in case of disruption, the driver sends a notification to the TMS where the recomputation of ETA is done	GPS position	KEYSTONE web app (GPS from driver device)	disruption event (standard data?) is sent to TMS
itinerary details	3	the web app receives/requests the updated ETA and the visualization of ETA is updated accordingly	updated ETA (recomputed by TMS)	GRUBER	visualization
notification about congestions	4	Display notification about congestion at the port gate	textual message sent by port operator	KEYSTONE web app	visualization

Driver Web app

